

Addenda and Corrigenda

to

Raoul Zamponi and Bernard Comrie
A Grammar of Akajeru
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In these Addenda and Corrigenda, in addition to minor corrections, we have tried to provide identification and current scientific names for biota (flora, fauna, etc.), following the more extensive presentation in Comrie and Zamponi (2026), which should be consulted for further details and for references. As in that work, the symbol [?] indicates lack of certainty on our part.

pp.72-73, headword **bido**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Calamus longisetus*

p.75, headword **bol'**

After “fish found in inland creeks” add reference: (RB2: 97).

p.98, headword **kelil**

(Portman 1887: 199) > (RB2: 199)

p.102–103

The headwords **kəroʃop** and **kəroin** are in inverted alphabetical order.

p.103, headword **kəroin**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Dipterocarpus turbinatus* [?]

p.105, headword **laro**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Erythrina variegata* [?]

p.106, headword **lito**

(RB2: 52) > (RB2: 152)

p.110, headword **mirid**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The scientific name *Columba livia* does not, however, correspond to Imperial pigeon

p.124–125, headword **ortfubi**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Ophiophagus hannah*

p.127, headword **poramo**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Knema linifolia* [?], but the species identification is uncertain, as we have not found this species attested in the Andamans

p.127, headword **poitfo**

Sterculia macrophylla > *Sterculia macrophylla* [?]

p.128, headword **pulimu**

Fly sp. > Fly sp.: *Musca domestica*

PGA *p^hulemu* ‘fly’ (Abbi 2012: 380) > PGA *p^hulemu* ‘a kind of fly *Musca domestica*’ (Abbi 2012: 108)

p.130, headword **rejo**

Add at the end of the entry a second Note:

Notes:

...

The current recommended scientific name is *Ficus altissima* [?]

p.136, headword **terkobito balo**

sandens > *scandens*

p.145, headword **tfelebi**

At the end of the Akachari comparison, add reference: (Portman 1887: 221)

p.146, headword **tfelene** (starts p.145)

celene ‘bird, crab Plover’ (Abbi 2012: 23, 337) > ‘crab plover, *Dromas ardeola*’ (Pande and Abbi: 19)

And add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name for *Buteroides striatus* (more usually *Butorides striata*) is *Butorides atricapella*

p.146, headword **ʔelmo**

Tree sp.: *Tetranthera lancifolia* > Tree sp.: *Tetranthera lancifolia* [?], *Tetranthera lanceifolia* [?]

And add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The species identification is uncertain, as it is unclear whether the spelling in the original corresponds to the older scientific name *Tetranthera lancifolia* (current scientific name *Litsea lancifolia*) or the older scientific name *Tetranthera lanceifolia* (current scientific name *Litsea salicifolia*), and we have found neither species attested in the Andamans

p.147, headword **ʔfo**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Entada rheedei* subspecies *rheedei* [?]

p.148, headword **ʔoleke**

Pterocarpus dalbergioides > *Pterocarpus dalbergioides* [?]

p.150, headword **ʔugotɔ**

Add at the end of the entry:

Notes:

The current recommended scientific name is *Manilkara littoralis* [?]

p.154, headword **creeper sp.**, Item Creeper sp.: *Pothos sandens*:

sandens > *scandens*

p.155, headword **fly sp.:**

Fly sp. > Fly sp.: *Musca domestica*

p.157, headword **insect sp.**, Item Fly sp.

Fly sp. > Fly sp.: *Musca domestica*

p.157, headword **insect sp.:**

Remove “Centipede” and “Spider” from this list. The separate headword entries for **centipede** on p.153 and for **spider** on p.163 are correct.

p.160, headword **plant sp.:**

Remove “Mushroom sp.” from this list. The separate headword entry for **mushroom sp.** on p.159 is correct.

p.161, headword **plant sp.** (starts p.160), Item Tree sp.: *Tetranthera lancifolia*

Tetranthera lancifolia > *Tetranthera lancifolia* [?], *Tetranthera lanceifolia* [?]

p.164, headword **tree sp.**, Item Tree sp.: *Tetranthera lancifolia*

Tetranthera lancifolia > *Tetranthera lancifolia* [?] *Tetranthera lanceifolia* [?]

p.168: Add the following new reference:

Comrie, Bernard and Raoul Zamponi. 2026. Flora and fauna terms in traditional Great Andamanese languages. <https://zenodo.org/records/18748966>